

Integration of multi-zone dynamic energy simulations into life cycle assessment for residential building renovation

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Abstract

The renovation rate of the building stock should increase to reach the 2050 climate goals. To develop carbon efficient renovation strategies, both the operational and embodied Environmental Impact (EI) should be considered. However, the operational energy use in Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) is often calculated by a simplified, steady-state approach.

This research investigates the influence of using dynamic simulations in LCA, focussing on the impact of occupant behaviour. A multi-zone dynamic simulation model of an archetype dwelling is used to come to a distribution of operational EI's. These results are combined with the embodied EI to perform an LCA of eleven different renovation scenarios.

The study finds that both comfort preference levels and insulation strategies (choice of insulation + finishing materials) significantly affect the total EI of renovation scenarios, and thus the most optimal renovation scenario. Further, comparing dynamic simulation results with those of the Belgian LCA tool TOTEM reveals large discrepancies due to simplified energy use calculations used in TOTEM.

Key Innovations

- Integrating dynamic Building Energy Simulations (BES) within LCA.
- Investigating the influence of user behaviour on LCA calculations through a dynamic BES-model.

Practical Implications

The results of this research can be used to adapt renovation methods to the specific occupant behaviour and choice of insulation materials in dwellings.

The comparison with the Belgian LCA tool TOTEM makes it relevant for practitioners in the field as well.

Introduction

The building sector plays a crucial role in achieving the 2050 climate goals. Therefore, the European Commission (n.d.) is committed to increase the renovation rate of the building stock. Buildings should be renovated to reduce the energy demand and make low-temperature heating possible in order to shift away from fossil fuels and facilitate the use of renewable and residual energy sources (R²ES). In this context, the Horizon Europe Mission

Project Neutralpath (n.d.) has been initiated. This project investigates how Positive and Clean Energy Districts (PCEDs) can be achieved in 5 European cities, in an inclusive manner. In Ghent, research is done to find the most optimal renovation scenarios in an existing district.

However, as the buildings become more energy efficient during the use stage, the share of the embodied Environmental Impact (EI) increases due to an increase in insulation materials. In order to study the optimal renovation scenarios in a holistic manner, both the operational EI related to the energy use during the use stage and the embodied EI related to material use during production, construction, use, and end-of-life stages should be taken into account (Trigaux et al., 2023).

In general, only limited research has been done on the implementation of dynamic energy simulations in Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) and the variability introduced by occupant behaviour. For example, the Belgian TOTEM tool which is commonly used in LCA in Belgium, uses simplified energy calculations via the Equivalent Heating Degree Days (EHDD) method (Trigaux et al., 2023).

Previous research by Ramon et al. (2023) compared results of multi-zone dynamic simulations in office buildings to the results of TOTEM v2.2. The comparison showed that TOTEM overestimates the environmental impact related to gas use by a factor two compared to the dynamic simulations with EnergyPlus. This overestimation was mainly related to two assumptions in TOTEM v2.2: no ventilation heat recovery is included and a default airtightness of 12 m³/(h.m²) is assumed. However, in the current version TOTEM v3.3.4 (2025), it is possible to choose from three different levels of airtightness and to select mechanical ventilation with heat recovery.

Further, the study by Ramon et al. (2023) indicated that current LCA approaches do not incorporate occupant behaviour. While this is less critical for office buildings, the focus of this research is on residential buildings, where occupant behavior varies significantly. Therefore, this research emphasizes the impact of occupant behaviour on LCA outcomes.

Reference building

An archetype dwelling of a typical 2-storey terraced house of the case study district in Ghent is set up to conduct the research, as shown in Figure 1. The main volume has a pitched roof, while the kitchen extension on the ground floor has a flat roof.

The archetype dwelling is based on previous research of Decorte (2024), which in turn drew upon previous research that identified archetypes that were considered representative of Flanders. The geometry has been slightly adapted to be coherent with the typology in the district.

Figure 1: archetype dwelling with 4 bedrooms.

Building Energy Simulation (BES) model

A BES-model is set up in Dymola, using the IDEAS library to model the building (Jorissen et al., 2018) and a Typical Meteorological Year (TMY) file of Ghent of 2001-2020 for the climate data (Machard, 2024).

Structure model

The BES-model consists of several sub-models. At first, a 4-zone structure model that represents the archetype dwelling is set up. Zone 1 includes the living and kitchen, zone 2 the hallway, zone 3 the bedrooms, and zone 4 the bathroom. The number of zones is kept as low as possible to reduce the complexity of the model, while still allowing for variation in use and setpoint temperatures in the different rooms.

The party walls are modelled as adiabatic boundaries, taking no transmission losses to the neighbours into account. The airtightness is varied among the different renovation scenarios, ranging from an n_{50} -value of 6 ACH, which is in line with the default value according to NBN EN 12831-1 ANB (2020) to an n_{50} -value of 3 ACH, assuming that the building airtightness improves by a factor two after renovation (Decorte, 2024).

Heating model

A simplified heating model is composed in IDEAS. A fixed heating power is provided to the zones in order to reach the desired setpoint temperature, with a bandwidth of 1°C. The heating powers in the model are calculated based on the emission power calculation prescribed in NBN EN 12831-1 (2017). However, since the heating system is only activated upon occupancy it can take some time to reach comfort temperatures when occupants are present, especially in the bathroom.

No heating power was added to the hallway, as the hallways of the investigated case study dwellings in Ghent were not equipped with radiators either.

Ventilation model

A mechanical exhaust ventilation system is implemented in the ventilation model, with a fixed supply flow of outdoor air in the living room and bedrooms and a fixed exhaust flow in the kitchen, bathroom, and hallway.

The supply flow and exhaust flow equal 228 m³/h, following the EPB calculation method in Flanders. (Vlaanderen, 2024; Vlaanderen, n.d.)

Occupant model

The thermal heat gains of the occupants together with the internal heat gains of electrical appliances and the setpoint temperatures of the zones at each timestep are implemented through the occupant model. This occupant behaviour is defined by the EROB-model, explained in the next paragraph.

Occupant behaviour modelling

EROB-model

The Event-based Residential Occupant Behaviour (EROB) model, developed by Verbruggen (2021), is used to estimate the energy demand for heating in an accurate manner with realistic occupant behaviour.

The EROB-model creates statistically representative sets of occupant behaviour that serve as input for dynamic simulations. These are expressed as time series profiles with a 10-minute resolution. For this research, the relevant outputs consist of internal heat gains and space

heating setpoint/setback (setp/setb) temperatures at each timestep for a predefined time span, one year in this case. To generate these profiles, the model requires inputs such as the number of household members and their employment types, the number of bedrooms, and the presence of electrical appliances. These inputs can either be explicitly defined by the modeller, or selected automatically by the model in a statistically representative manner.

Enhancements to the EROB model

To more accurately investigate the heating demand of dwellings using dynamic simulations, the EROB-model was refined to allow a more detailed representation of occupant behaviour. Setpoint temperature time series are now generated per room rather than per zone, enabling differentiation in both temperature and heating duration between individual bedrooms. Further, the calculation of metabolic heat gains from occupants has been improved by incorporating not only activity level, but also weight, height, gender, and age.

Table 1: occupant profiles and the accompanying setpoint temperatures for space heating.

nr.	Nr. of occupants	Employment type	Nr. of occupied bedrooms
1	2	2x Full Time Employed (FTE)	1
2	5	FTE, Unemployed, 3x Child	4
Comfort preference		Space heating profile	Rooms heated
1	low	low setp, small setb (15°C) when asleep and away	living and kitchen (17°C), bathroom (19°C), no bedrooms
	medium	medium setp, high setb (12°C) when asleep	living and kitchen (19.5°C), bathroom (22°C), 1 bedroom (17.5°C)
	high	high setp, never setb	living and kitchen (21.5°C), bathroom (22.2°C), 1 bedroom (18.5°C)
2	low/medium	low setp, small setb (17°C) when asleep	living and kitchen (19.5°C), bathroom (20.5°C), no bedrooms
	high	high setp, never setb	living and kitchen (22.1°C), bathroom (24.3°C), 4 bedrooms (19 °C)

Implementation of the EROB model

The EROB-model is implemented in the BES-model through the occupant model. The setpoint temperatures are defined in different manners. The living room and kitchen are combined in one open space in the case study. Hence, the entire zone is heated to the highest desired setpoint temperature of these rooms. On the other hand,

the four bedrooms are modelled as a single zone, whereas in reality the setpoint temperatures can be defined individually per room. To estimate the heating demand as accurately as possible, the volume weighted setpoint temperature for this zone is defined per timestep of 10 minutes. The setpoint temperatures for the bathroom and hallway coincide with the zones and are used directly. The convective and radiative internal heat gains of the occupants are also implemented directly.

Occupant profiles

Table 1 gives an overview of the occupant profiles used in this research. The profiles are generated by the EROB model in a statistically representative manner. The only input given to the model was the number of bedrooms, the number of occupants and the comfort preferences of the users, with low, medium or high setpoints.

With these profiles, the impact of the heating behaviour of the occupants is investigated. Further, as also the number of occupants and the accompanying number of heated bedrooms differs, the impact of heating or not heating the rooms under the roof is examined as well.

Table 1 indicates whether a setback temperature is used or not. This temperature only applies to the living room and kitchen. The other rooms always have a setback temperature of 12°C when unoccupied, which is the same setpoint temperature of the unheated rooms.

Renovation scenarios of the construction components

Table 2 shows the 11 renovation scenarios that are applied to investigate the EI of light to deep energy renovations.

Table 2: U-values of the construction components for the 11 renovation scenarios; grey text indicates existing uninsulated construction components; black text indicates new insulated components.

nr.	Slab on grade [W/(m²K)]	Walls [W/(m²K)]	Windows [W/(m²K)]	Pitched roof [W/(m²K)]	Flat roof [W/(m²K)]
1	0.83	1.70	1.41	2.23	1.42
2	0.83	0.24	2.86	2.23	1.42
3	0.83	1.70	2.86	0.24	0.24
4	0.24	1.70	2.86	2.23	1.42
5	0.83	0.55	1.41	2.23	1.42
6	0.83	0.24	1.41	2.23	1.42
7	0.83	0.24	2.86	0.24	0.24
8	0.83	1.70	1.41	0.24	0.24
9	0.83	0.24	1.41	2.23	0.24
10	0.83	0.24	1.41	0.24	0.24
11	0.24	0.24	1.41	0.24	0.24

The U-values for the insulated walls relate to 2 different insulation measures: exterior insulation (0.24 W/(m²K)) or retrofit cavity wall insulation (0.55 W/(m²K)).

For the windows, a g-value of 0.78 is assumed for existing double glazing (U = 2.86 W/(m²K)) and a g-value of 0.55 for new high performance double glazing (U = 1.41 W/(m²K)).

Life Cycle Assessment (LCA)

Methodology

In Belgium, a Tool to Optimise the Total Environmental impact of Materials (TOTEM) was created in 2014 to calculate the EI of buildings in the Belgian context. The environmental data to calculate the EI is mainly derived from the Ecoinvent database. For this research, the methodology of TOTEM v3.3.4 is used.

This tool allows to calculate the total EI of renovated buildings, as a sum of the embodied EI and operational EI. The embodied EI takes into account the impact of new, existing, and demolished materials. For the new materials, the product stage and construction process stage (modules A1-5), the maintenance and replacement (respectively module B2, and B4), and the end-of-life stage (modules C1-4) are considered. For the materials that are preserved, modules B2, B4, and C1-4 are taken into account and for materials that are removed, modules C1-4 are accounted for. The operational EI only takes module B6 into account, the operational energy use. Both the embodied EI and operational EI are calculated over a study period of 60 years.

The environmental impact is quantified as an aggregated single-score, expressed in milli-points [mPt]. This score covers 19 environmental impact indicators specified by EN 15804+A2. The indicators address a broad spectrum of environmental issues, such as climate change, ozone depletion, acidification, water consumption, particulate matter formation, and eco-toxicity. The aggregation is performed using Product Environmental Footprint (PEF) normalization and weighting factors. In addition to this single-score result, the climate change impact is also reported separately, expressed in [kg CO₂ eq.] which is an indicator for global warming potential. (Trigaux, et al., 2023).

Embodied EI

For the embodied EI, only the impact of the building envelope is taken into account. Based on previous research of Decorte (2024), a preliminary analysis has been done to select assemblies with a low embodied EI and assemblies with a high embodied EI per construction component, for the same U-value. These two build-ups with different levels of embodied EI are selected, as the choice of the insulation strategy also reflects the occupant behaviour.

The embodied EI of the 11 renovation scenarios is calculated for both the low and high EI insulation strategies applying the TOTEM methodology, but with data from previous research of Decorte (2024), that is mostly based on the Ecoinvent database. This approach was necessary because of the limitations of the TOTEM (2025) database of construction components, which does not fully correspond with the build-ups used in this study. Additionally, module B2 is excluded in this research due to its user-specific nature and limited data availability.

Operational EI

In TOTEM (2025), the energy use to estimate the operational EI is calculated using the EHDD method,

which incorporates transmission and ventilation losses. A fixed number of 1200 equivalent degree-days is used, corresponding to a well-insulated dwelling with an average indoor temperature of 18°C.

The results from this calculation are then converted to a final energy use by taking into account a distribution, emission, and control efficiency of respectively 0.95, 0.95 and 0.94 for a typical residential heating installation and a seasonal production efficiency of 2.9 for an air-to-water heat pump, assuming an air-to-water heat pump is used in all renovation scenarios. This final energy use is then multiplied with an environmental impact factor of the Belgian electricity mix of 7.39E-3 mPt per MJ or 6.89E-2 kg CO₂ eq. per MJ to come to an operational EI.

To make a fair comparison of the operational EI of space heating of the BES model to the EHDD method of TOTEM, the same distribution, emission, and control efficiency are accounted for in the BES-model, as well as the same environmental impact factor of the Belgian electricity mix. However, the efficiency of the heat pump is quite low in TOTEM. To come to more realistic results and to assess the ratio of embodied EI to total EI correctly for the BES-simulations, a Seasonal Coefficient of Performance (SCOP) of 3.25 is used to account for a heat pump at a regime of 55/45°C (Department for Energy Security & Net Zero, n.d.). This will however cause a small additional difference between the estimated operational EI of TOTEM and the BES-simulations.

Further, a climate data file of Ghent is used in the BES-model, while TOTEM accounts for 1200 equivalent degree-days by default (Trigaux, et al., 2023).

Results

The single score and climate change results are presented in Figure 2 and Figure 3, respectively.

The bars depict the outcomes of the dynamic simulations across all renovation scenarios, while the symbols represent the corresponding results obtained using the EHDD method.

Occupant profile 1

The results for the first occupant profile are shown in Figures 2 and 3. When comparing the different comfort preference profiles, the overall trend among renovation scenarios based on operational EI mostly remains consistent, but there is a significant impact on the absolute operational EI. On average, the operational EI increases by 57% from a low to a medium comfort preference profile and by 76% from a low to a high comfort preference profile. Conversely, going from 1 to 2–2.5 renovation measures within the same comfort preference level reduces the operational EI by 18–23% on average, and going from 1 to 3–4 renovation measures results in a reduction of 59–71%. In most scenarios, insulating more construction components would thus not compensate for the increased operational EI if the occupants would shift from a low to a medium or from a medium to a high comfort preference profile after renovation.

Further, it is also clear that the choice of insulation strategies for the construction components has a large influence on the embodied EI. The embodied EI of the renovation scenarios is 38% to 119% higher for insulation strategies with a high EI compared to strategies with a low EI for the single-score results and respectively 52% to 179% higher for the climate change results.

The large differences between the various comfort preference profiles and insulation strategies also influences the ratio of embodied EI to total EI. For scenario 11 (full renovation), this ratio ranges from 35% to 59% for insulation strategies with a low EI and from 51% to 73% for high EI insulation strategies for the different comfort preference profiles as a single-score

result and respectively from 37% to 61% and from 54% to 76% for the climate change results.

These discrepancies also influence the optimal renovation scenario per comfort preference profile. When adopting insulation methods with a low EI, it is always best to insulate all construction components (scenario 11) according to the single-score results and the global warming results.

For insulation methods with a high EI, the results show larger differences, depending on the comfort preference level. Regarding the single-score results, renovation scenario 7 (insulating the walls and roofs) and scenario 10 (renovating all construction components except for the slab on grade) score better than the full renovation for a low comfort preference profile. At medium and high

Figure 2: Single-score environmental impact results of the 11 renovation scenarios categorised per comfort level preference and occupant profile, where the operational energy use was calculated both with BES and EHDD.

Figure 3: Climate change environmental impact results of the 11 renovation scenarios categorised per comfort level preference and occupant profile, where the operational energy use was calculated both with BES and EHDD.

comfort preference levels, renovation scenario 11 performs best, though scenarios 7 and 10 also show significantly better results than the other renovation scenarios. Concerning the climate change results, renovation scenario 7 consistently scores best, regardless of the comfort preference profile, with EI savings up to 24% compared to the full renovation. For the low comfort preference profile, renovation scenarios 3 (insulating the roofs), and 10 also score slightly better than a full renovation. However, scenario 7 still scores best.

If a full renovation is not feasible, e.g., due to financial constraints, only renovating the windows is one of the less favourable options based on the total EI. It shows the highest operational EI, partly due to a decreased g-value after renovation of the windows resulting in fewer solar heat gains in winter, and they have a high embodied impact.

Depending on the boundary conditions, only renovating the slab on grade can even have a higher total EI than only renovating the windows. Although the operational EI is lower in this scenario, the embodied EI is much higher than for windows, even up to 79% higher when comparing renovation strategies with a low embodied EI, causing a high total EI for scenario 4 (insulating the slab on grade). This is due to the renovation scenario assumed. In the existing scenario, only a screed and floor finishing are present on top of a layer of compacted sand. When insulating the floor, a concrete floor slab is cast and a new floor finishing is required, causing a high environmental impact for renovation. However, when carrying out a full renovation (scenario 10 or 11), it is still better in most cases to also include the slab on grade, apart from the scenario with low comfort preferences and insulation materials with a high embodied EI.

When only one measure can be implemented, it is best to first insulate the roofs (scenario 3) in all cases. If two measures can be implemented, it is best to insulate both roofs and walls (scenario 7).

Comparing renovation scenario 9 (renovating walls, windows, and flat roof) to renovation scenario 10, makes it clear that it is preferable to not only renovate the flat roof, but also the pitched roof. The additional embodied EI of renovating the pitched roof in scenario 10 is fully compensated by the operational EI savings compared to scenario 9. The total EI of scenario 10 is up to 46 or 45% lower compared to renovation scenario 9 for insulation strategies with a low EI and up to 36 or 35% lower for strategies with a high EI, respectively for the single-score and climate change results.

Occupant profile 2

Figures 2 and 3 also show the results for occupant profile two, where all four bedrooms are occupied. It still shows the same overall trend among the renovation scenarios as occupant profile one.

For the high comfort preference profile, the operational EI is higher for occupant profile two than for occupant profile one in most of the renovation scenarios, as would be expected since more bedrooms are heated. However,

for some renovation scenarios, this shifts. The operational EI for occupant two is 4% to 20% lower compared to occupant one for renovation scenario 7, 8, 10 and 11. This seems to imply that when the house is (almost) fully insulated, it is more energy efficient to also heat the top floor, but it is more likely a result of the higher internal heat gains of occupant two, that become increasingly important when the house is better insulated.

Further, mostly the same conclusions can be drawn on the preferred renovation scenarios as for occupant profile one. Two minor exceptions are that when the insulation strategies with a high EI are considered for the climate change results, renovation scenario 3 does not perform better than scenario 11 for the low/medium comfort preference profile, but scenario 10 slightly scores better than scenario 11 in the high comfort preference profile.

As all bedrooms are heated for the high comfort preference level in occupant profile two, the preference for also renovating the pitched roof and not only the flat roof becomes even more outspoken when comparing renovation scenario 10 to scenario 9. The total EI of scenario 10 is even up to 55% lower compared to renovation scenario 9 for insulation strategies with a low EI and 49 or 48% lower for strategies with a high EI for respectively the single-score and climate change results.

Comparison with TOTEM (EHDD method)

Figures 2 and 3 also include the results of the TOTEM tool using the EHDD method. As this method takes no variations in occupant behaviour into account, the results are the same for all occupant profiles. Consequently, large over- and underestimations of the operational EI can be found in the low and high comfort preference profiles.

For renovation scenarios 1, 2, 3 and 4, with only one renovation measure taken, this causes overestimations of the operational EI up to 88% for the low comfort preference profile and underestimations up to 27% for the high comfort preference profile. However, for deep renovations (scenario 10 and 11), the operational EI is overestimated in all comfort preference profiles. The shift from underestimating the operational EI for the light renovation scenarios to overestimating the EI for deeper renovations within the high comfort preference profiles is a consequence of the simplified calculation approach of the EHDD method. This takes into account a fixed number of equivalent degree-days, corresponding to a well-insulated dwelling. As not-well-insulated dwellings require more heating days, this number of equivalent degree-days leads to underestimations of the heating demand.

Further, the operational EI aligns most closely with the medium comfort preference profile of occupant one. However, also in this case, the operational EI for the light renovation scenarios tends to be underestimated, while the operational EI for deep renovations is overestimated.

Discussion

The results indicate that incorporating user behaviour significantly impacts the total EI of various renovation scenarios. When only comparing the operational energy

use of the different renovation scenarios, a deep energy renovation is always preferred. However, when combining LCA with BES-simulations that incorporate occupant behaviour, the results are more differentiated and become dependent on the choice of the insulation strategies (choice of insulation + finishing materials) and comfort preference levels of the occupants.

This approach can thus help optimise energy renovations tailored to specific occupant behaviour. However, when household composition changes or the dwelling is occupied by new residents, the initially selected renovation measures may no longer be optimal. In such cases, either more or fewer measures might have performed better according to the LCA. This raises the question of whether it is preferable to design for the highest level of comfort preference by default. These trade-offs, however, can only be effectively evaluated when occupant behaviour is integrated into LCA.

Nevertheless, tools like TOTEM are designed for easy use by a wide audience in the building sector, providing quick results and easily accommodating variations in building geometry. This ease of use is a significant advantage compared to BES-models. However, due to simplified calculation methods, these tools currently cannot account for variations in user behaviour. Therefore, further research on the influence of occupant behaviour is necessary.

Conclusion

This paper examines how dynamic building energy simulations that account for different occupant behaviours affect the results of building Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) across 11 renovation scenarios. It considers both low and high environmental impact insulation methods. The analysis is done for 2 different occupant profiles, one that only uses one bedroom at the first floor and one that occupies all bedrooms at the first and second floor. A distinction is made between low, medium, and high comfort preference profiles in terms of setpoint temperatures.

(1) The occupant behaviour, both in terms of comfort preference profile and choice of insulation methods has a large impact on the total EI of the different renovation scenarios. The operational EI increases by 76% on average going from a low to a high comfort preference profile, while in the EHDD method of TOTEM this difference is neglected. Further, within the same renovation scenarios, using insulation strategies with a high embodied EI instead of low embodied EI alternatives leads to an increase in embodied EI ranging from 38% to 119% for the single-score results, and from 52% to 179% for the climate change results.

(2) These two phenomena also influence the ratio of embodied EI to total EI. For a full renovation, this ratio ranges from 35% up to 73% for the single-score results and from 37% to 76% for the climate change results, depending on the insulation strategy and comfort preference profile.

(3) When renovating with materials with a low embodied EI, a full renovation results in the lowest EI. However, when choosing insulation methods with a high embodied EI, the results differ among the different comfort preference profiles, e.g., when solely considering the climate change results, it is best to only renovate the roofs and walls for all comfort preference profiles.

(4) If a full renovation is not feasible, the roofs are the most favourable insulation options. Replacing the windows or insulating the slab on grade are less favourable as first measure in terms of EI.

(5) When comparing the BES results to the EHDD results, it is found that the EHDD results mostly coincide with the medium comfort preference profiles, but there are still discrepancies between the results due to the simplifications in the EHDD method. For the other comfort profiles, large over- and underestimations of the operational EI are found in the results, because the EHDD method does not take occupant behaviour into account.

(6) The research points out that taking occupant behaviour into account influences the life cycle EI of buildings significantly, as both the operational EI and embodied EI are affected by the occupant.

As a perspective for further research, on the one hand sensitivity analyses could be conducted to investigate the impact of e.g. climate change and different climate zones, as well as incorporating different efficiencies of the air-to-water heat pump depending on the insulation level of the dwelling. On the other hand, further research is essential to achieve results that are generally applicable across different occupant profiles, energy consumption patterns, renovation scenarios, and building typologies. This will enable the formulation of comprehensive guidelines for building renovations.

Acknowledgement

Funded by the European Union under the EU Programme HORIZON-MISS-2021-CIT-02-04 under Grant Agreement No. n°: 101096753. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the authors only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. The European Union cannot be held responsible for them.

References

- TOTEM - Versie 3.3.4. (2025). TOTEM. <https://www.totem-building.be/home.xhtml>
- Bureau for Standardisation. (2017). NBN EN 12831-1:2017: Energy performance of buildings - Method for calculation of the design heat load - Part 1: Space heating load.
- Bureau voor normalisatie. (2020). NBN EN 12831-1 ANB: 2020: Energieprestatie van gebouwen - Methode voor de berekening van de ontwerpwarmtebelasting - Deel 1: Warmtebemesting voor ruimteverwarming - Nationale bijlage.
- Decorte, Y. (2024). Three pathways towards a sustainable transition of Flemish dwellings : what are the shifts in the environmental trade-off? Doctoral dissertation,

- Ghent University. Faculty of Engineering and Architecture, Ghent, Belgium.
- Department for Energy Security & Net Zero. (n.d.). Air to Water Heat Pumps. Energy Technology List. <https://etl.energysecurity.gov.uk/products/heat-pumps/air-water-heat-pumps>
- European Commission. (n.d.). Renovation Wave. Energy. Retrieved on February 19, 2025 from https://energy.ec.europa.eu/topics/energy-efficiency/energy-efficient-buildings/renovation-wave_en
- Jorissen, F., Reynders, G. et al. (2018). Implementation and verification of the IDEAS building energy simulation library. *Journal of Building Performance Simulation* (11). 669 – 688.
- Machard, A., Salvati, A. Et al. (2024). IEA EBC Annex 80 "Typical and extreme weather datasets for studying the resilience of buildings to climate change" (Version 1.0). World Data Center for Climate (WDCC) at DKRZ. https://doi.org/10.26050/WDCC/WDTF_Annex80_build_v1.0
- Neutralpath. (n.d.). Ghent. 2030 Neutralpath. Retrieved February 19, 2025, from <https://neutralpath.eu/city/ghent/>
- Ramon, D., Allacker, K. et al. (2023). Dynamic modelling of operational energy use in a building LCA: A case study of a Belgian office building. *Energy and Buildings* (278). 112634- 112649.
- Trigaux, D. Lam, W. Et al. (2023). Environmental profile of buildings [update 2023]. Belgium: TOTEM.
- Verbruggen, S. (2021). Window use habits as an example of habitual occupant behaviour in residential buildings. Ghent: Ghent University.
- Vlaanderen (2024). Energiebesluit bijlage V - bepalingsmethode van het peil van primair energieverbruik van residentiële eenheden. EPB-PEDIA voor professionelen. chrome-extension://efaidnbmnnnibpcajpcglclefindmkaj/https://assets.vlaanderen.be/image/upload/v1733929214/Bijlage_EPW_20231020_vergunningenNA2025_DRAFT_mcmrsn.pdf
- Vlaanderen. (n.d.). Minimaal geëiste ontwerpdebiet (residentieel). EPB-PEDIA voor professionelen. Retrieved on March 3, 2025 from <https://www.vlaanderen.be/epb-pedia/technieken/ventilatie/hygiënische-ventilatie/hygiënische-ventilatie-nieuwbouw-en-ier-residentieel/minimaal-geëiste-ontwerpdebiet-residentieel>